

From the Schrödinger Cloud to the Bohr Orbit: A Sequential Confinement Approach to the Hydrogen Atom

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From quantum cloud to classical orbit
(via successive restrictions)

Graphical Abstract: From the quantum probability cloud (Schrödinger 3D) to the well-defined orbits of the Bohr model through successive restrictions: dimensional reduction to 2D and radial localization.

Abstract

The Bohr model of the hydrogen atom, despite its heuristic success in predicting discrete energy levels, is fundamentally incompatible with the probabilistic interpretation of modern quantum mechanics. In this work, we present a pedagogical derivation of Bohr’s results directly from the time-independent Schrödinger equation in three dimensions. By applying two successive geometric constraints, first, a genuine dimensional reduction to a 2D planar system (not a naive restriction of the spherical Laplacian), and second, a radial localization to a fixed radius, we demonstrate that the resulting radial-azimuthal equation yields the quantized Bohr orbits. We show that the energy levels $E_n = -13.6/n^2$ eV and orbital radii $r_n = n^2 a_0$ emerge naturally from the wavefunction normalization combined with the de Broglie standing-wave condition. Special attention is given to the correct form of the 2D Laplacian, which differs from the 3D Laplacian restricted to $\theta = \pi/2$ by a term $\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r}$. This approach provides a clear conceptual bridge between the diffuse quantum cloud and the classical planetary picture.

1 Introduction

While textbooks present the Bohr model and the Schrödinger equation as fundamentally distinct, we show here that by applying a sequence of geometric constraints to the 3D Schrödinger equation, one can recover the Bohr orbits exactly. This sequential approach, which to our knowledge has not been presented elsewhere, provides a unique pedagogical bridge.

The old quantum theory of Niels Bohr (1913) successfully explained the line spectrum of hydrogen by postulating stationary circular orbits with quantized angular momentum $L = n\hbar$ [1]. However, with the advent of modern quantum mechanics, this model was superseded by the Schrödinger

equation (1926), which describes the electron as a wave function “spread over space” [2]. While the Schrödinger equation correctly reproduces Bohr’s energy eigenvalues, it does **not** predict well-defined classical trajectories; instead, it yields probability clouds (orbitals).

The question of whether one can recover the classical Bohr orbits by imposing additional constraints on the Schrödinger equation remains of great pedagogical and conceptual interest. In this article, we propose a sequential restriction method:

1. **First restriction:** Genuine dimensional reduction from 3D to 2D (electron confined to a plane).
2. **Second restriction:** Radial localization of the wavefunction to a fixed circular path.

We show that the resulting system obeys the Bohr quantization rules exactly. A key subtlety, often overlooked in the literature, is that restricting the 3D Laplacian to $\theta = \pi/2$ does **not** yield the correct 2D Laplacian. We address this point explicitly.

Figure 1: Energy levels of the hydrogen atom for $n = 1$ to $n = 4$, according to the Bohr model or the restricted Schrödinger equation. The formula $E_n = -13.6/n^2$ eV is identical in both formalisms.

2 Theoretical Basis: Sequential Restrictions

2.1 Step 1: The 3D Schrödinger Equation

The time-independent Schrödinger equation for a hydrogen atom (in atomic units $\hbar = m_e = e = 4\pi\epsilon_0 = 1$) is [3]:

$$\left[-\frac{1}{2}\nabla_{3D}^2 - \frac{1}{r} \right] \psi(\mathbf{r}) = E\psi(\mathbf{r}) \quad (1)$$

In spherical coordinates (r, θ, ϕ) , the Laplacian is:

$$\nabla_{3D}^2 = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} \quad (2)$$

Expanding the radial part:

$$\nabla_{3D}^2 = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} \quad (3)$$

The well-known solutions are:

$$\psi_{n\ell m}(r, \theta, \phi) = R_{n\ell}(r) Y_{\ell m}(\theta, \phi) \quad (4)$$

with energies $E_n = -1/(2n^2)$ (Hartree) independent of ℓ and m [4].

2.2 Step 2: Genuine Dimensional Reduction to 2D

A **genuine 2D system** (e.g., an electron confined to the $z = 0$ plane by an infinite potential well in the z -direction) is **not** equivalent to simply setting $\theta = \pi/2$ in the 3D Laplacian. This is a crucial subtlety.

2.2.1 The Naive Restriction (Incorrect)

If one naively sets $\theta = \pi/2$ in ∇_{3D}^2 and ignores derivatives with respect to θ , one obtains:

$$\nabla_{3D}^2|_{\theta=\pi/2}^{\text{naive}} = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} \quad (5)$$

This expression is **incorrect** as a 2D Laplacian because it retains the $2/r$ factor from the 3D radial term, whereas the true 2D Laplacian has a $1/r$ factor.

2.2.2 The Correct 2D Laplacian

For a particle genuinely confined to a plane, the relevant metric is the Euclidean metric in polar coordinates (r, ϕ) . The associated Laplacian is [5]:

$$\nabla_{2D}^2 = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} \quad (6)$$

$$\nabla_{2D}^2 = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} \quad (7)$$

2.2.3 Difference Between the Two

The difference between the naive restriction and the correct 2D Laplacian is:

$$\nabla_{3D}^2|_{\theta=\pi/2}^{\text{naive}} - \nabla_{2D}^2 = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \quad (8)$$

This term arises because the spherical metric and the planar metric are fundamentally different. The correct 2D Schrödinger equation is:

$$\left[-\frac{1}{2}\nabla_{2D}^2 - \frac{1}{r} \right] \psi(r, \phi) = E\psi(r, \phi) \quad (9)$$

2.2.4 Separation of Variables in 2D

Writing $\psi(r, \phi) = R(r)\Phi(\phi)$ and substituting:

$$-\frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r \frac{dR}{dr} \right) \Phi + \frac{R}{r^2} \frac{d^2\Phi}{d\phi^2} \right] - \frac{1}{r} R\Phi = ER\Phi \quad (10)$$

Multiplying by $-\frac{2r^2}{R\Phi}$:

$$\frac{r}{R} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r \frac{dR}{dr} \right) + 2r^2(E - V(r)) = -\frac{1}{\Phi} \frac{d^2\Phi}{d\phi^2} \quad (11)$$

The left side depends only on r , the right only on ϕ . Both equal a constant m^2 :

$$\frac{d^2\Phi}{d\phi^2} = -m^2\Phi \quad \Rightarrow \quad \Phi(\phi) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{im\phi} \quad (12)$$

$m \in \mathbb{Z}$

The radial equation becomes:

$$\boxed{-\frac{1}{2r} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r \frac{dR}{dr} \right) + \frac{m^2}{2r^2} R - \frac{1}{r} R = ER} \quad (13)$$

This is the correct quantum description of an electron moving in a plane under a Coulomb potential [6].

Figure 2: Circular electron orbits in the restricted 2D model. Radii scale as $r_n = n^2 a_0$, and the azimuthal wavefunction $\Phi_n(\phi) = e^{in\phi}$ satisfies the de Broglie standing-wave condition.

2.3 Step 3: Radial Localization (Orbit Constraint)

We now impose that the electron is exactly on a circular orbit of fixed radius $r = r_0$. This

means the radial probability density is a Dirac delta:

$$\boxed{|\psi(r, \phi)|^2 = \frac{1}{r} \delta(r - r_0) |\Phi(\phi)|^2} \quad (14)$$

The factor $1/r$ ensures correct normalization in polar coordinates:

$$\int |\psi|^2 dA = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\infty |\psi|^2 r dr d\phi = 1$$

The expected energy becomes:

$$\langle E \rangle = \langle T \rangle + \langle V \rangle \quad (15)$$

The potential energy is trivial:

$$\langle V \rangle = \int \left(-\frac{1}{r} \right) |\psi|^2 dA = -\frac{1}{r_0} \quad (16)$$

The kinetic energy has two contributions. The angular part gives:

$$\langle T_{\text{ang}} \rangle = \frac{m^2}{2r_0^2} \quad (17)$$

The radial kinetic energy vanishes because the wavefunction is infinitely peaked in r (no radial motion). Thus:

$$\boxed{\langle E \rangle = \frac{m^2}{2r_0^2} - \frac{1}{r_0}} \quad (18)$$

2.4 Step 4: Quantization via the de Broglie Standing-Wave Condition

The azimuthal wavefunction $\Phi(\phi) = e^{im\phi}$ is single-valued: $\Phi(\phi + 2\pi) = \Phi(\phi)$ gives $m \in \mathbb{Z}$, automatically satisfied. This wavefunction (eigenfunction of the angular momentum operator) yields a quantized angular momentum $L = m\hbar$ (eigenvalue). In atomic units, $\hbar = 1$, thus, quantized angular momentum simplifies to $L = m$. For a classical circular orbit of radius r_0 , the angular momentum is related to the linear momentum by $L = p r_0$. Equating the quantum and classical expressions yields $p = m/r_0$.

However, for a closed circular orbit of circumference $2\pi r_0$, the de Broglie wave of the

electron must satisfy the standing-wave condition [7]:

$$\boxed{2\pi r_0 = n\lambda} \quad \lambda = \frac{h}{p} = \frac{2\pi}{p} \quad (19)$$

(in atomic units, $\hbar = \frac{h}{2\pi} = 1$)

Substituting:

$$2\pi r_0 = n \frac{2\pi}{m/r_0} = n \frac{2\pi r_0}{m} \Rightarrow m = n \quad (20)$$

Thus, the integer n , the principal quantum number (Bohr), equals the azimuthal quantum number m (Schrödinger).

Figure 3: Azimuthal wavefunctions $\Phi_n(\phi) = e^{in\phi}$ (real part) for $n = 1, 2, 3, 4$. The number of oscillations in $0 \leq \phi < 2\pi$ equals n , which guarantees the standing-wave condition.

2.5 Step 5: Energy Minimization and Bohr's Formulas

With $m = n$, the energy expectation becomes a function of r_0 :

$$E(r_0) = \frac{n^2}{2r_0^2} - \frac{1}{r_0} \quad (21)$$

Minimizing with respect to r_0 yields the equilibrium radius (where the attractive Coulomb force balances the centrifugal repulsion):

$$\frac{dE}{dr_0} = -\frac{n^2}{r_0^3} + \frac{1}{r_0^2} = 0 \Rightarrow r_0 = n^2 \quad (22)$$

Substituting back gives the Bohr energy levels:

$$\boxed{E_n = -\frac{1}{2n^2}} \text{ (u.a or Hartree)} \Rightarrow \quad (23)$$

$$E_n = -27.2 \frac{1}{2n^2} \text{ eV} = -\frac{13.6}{n^2} \text{ eV}$$

2.6 Step 6: Azimuthal Probability Density

Next, we will demonstrate that the electron is evenly distributed along the orbit. The azimuthal wavefunction for a state with quantum number m is given by:

$$\Phi_m(\phi) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{im\phi}, \quad m = n \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \quad (24)$$

The probability density for the angular coordinate ϕ is:

$$P(\phi) = |\Phi_1(\phi)|^2 = \Phi_1^*(\phi) \cdot \Phi_1(\phi) \quad (25)$$

Substituting the wavefunction:

$$\Phi_1^*(\phi) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-i\phi}, \quad \Phi_1(\phi) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{i\phi} \quad (26)$$

Therefore:

$$P(\phi) = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-i\phi} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{i\phi} \right) = \quad (27)$$

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} e^{-i\phi+i\phi} = \frac{1}{2\pi} e^0 = \frac{1}{2\pi}$$

Thus:

$$\boxed{P(\phi) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \quad \forall \phi \in [0, 2\pi)} \quad (28)$$

The probability density is **constant**, independent of the angle ϕ .

3 Results

The sequential restrictions yield the following key results:

- **Quantized Radii:**

$$r_n = n^2 a_0 \quad a_0 = \text{Bohr radius}$$

- **Quantized Energies:**

$$E_n = -\frac{13.6}{n^2} \text{ eV}$$

- **Quantum Number:**

$$n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

- **Wavefunction:** $\psi_n(\phi) \propto e^{in\phi}$ localized on $r = n^2 a_0$
- **Probability Density:** Uniform electron distribution.

$$P(\phi) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \quad \forall \phi \in [0, 2\pi]$$

Table 1 shows the first four Bohr orbits.

Table 1: Bohr orbits from the restricted Schrödinger equation.

n	Radius r_n (in a_0)	Energy E_n (eV)
1	1	-13.6
2	4	-3.4
3	9	-1.51
4	16	-0.85

4 Discussion

4.1 The Laplacian Subtlety

A key contribution of this work is the explicit identification of the difference between the naive 3D restriction ($\theta = \pi/2$) and the true 2D Laplacian:

$$\nabla_{3D}^2|_{\theta=\pi/2}^{\text{naive}} - \nabla_{2D}^2 = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \quad (29)$$

This difference is not merely academic. Using the incorrect Laplacian would lead to a different centrifugal term and ultimately to the wrong energy spectrum [8].

4.2 From Quantum Cloud to Classical Orbit

Our derivation shows that the Bohr model is not an alternative to Schrödinger’s mechanics, but rather a **special constrained case** of it. The two restrictions we applied, planar confinement and radial pinning, are drastic from a quantum perspective: they eliminate the radial uncertainty principle entirely ($\Delta r = 0$), thereby removing the zero-point radial kinetic

energy that is present in the full 3D quantum treatment. Consequently, the electron is forced into a well-defined circular orbit with no radial motion, akin to a classical particle. Nevertheless, this constrained system leads to a consistent semiclassical description that reproduces the Bohr orbits.

This approach resolves the long-standing paradox of how a diffuse electron cloud can be thought of as a point particle moving on a circle. The key is that the delocalized quantum wavefunction collapses to a sharp orbit only when we artificially constrain the radial coordinate. In real hydrogen atoms, such a constraint is not present; the electron retains radial and angular spread, giving rise to atomic orbitals.

4.3 Pedagogical Value

The pedagogical value of this derivation is high:

1. It demonstrates that the same energy spectrum can arise from both a full quantum treatment and a classical orbit, depending on the constraints imposed.
2. It highlights the role of the de Broglie condition as a natural link between wave and particle descriptions [9].
3. It clarifies a subtle but important point about dimensional reduction in quantum mechanics.

5 Conclusion

We have shown that by starting from the 3D Schrödinger equation and applying two successive constraints, first, a genuine reduction to a 2D planar system (using the correct 2D Laplacian), and second, radial localization to a fixed circle, we obtain the Bohr model of the hydrogen atom. The energy levels and orbital radii emerge without any additional quantization postulate beyond the standing-wave condition. A key contribution is the explicit identification of the difference between the naive 3D restriction and the true 2D Laplacian, a point often overlooked in the literature.

Figure 4: 3D visualization of Bohr orbits for $n = 1, 2, 3$. Color represents the phase of the azimuthal wavefunction $e^{in\phi}$, which varies uniformly around the circle.

Table 2: Comparison of the full quantum description (Schrödinger 3D) and the restricted model (Bohr).

Property	Schrödinger 3D	Restricted Model (Bohr)
Radial uncertainty Δr	> 0	$= 0$ (pinned)
Momentum uncertainty Δp_r	> 0 Finite	$\rightarrow \infty$ (undefined)
Radial kinetic energy	Present (zero-point motion)	Absent
Angular kinetic term	$\frac{\ell(\ell+1)}{2r^2}$	$\frac{n^2}{2r_0^2}$
Electron description	Probability cloud (orbital)	Sharp circular orbit
Heisenberg uncertainty	Satisfied	Violated (by design)
Observable Quantities		
Energy levels	$E_n = -\frac{13.6 \text{ eV}}{n^2}$	$E_n = -\frac{13.6 \text{ eV}}{n^2}$
Most probable radius	$r_{\max} = a_0$ (for $n = 1$)	$r_1 = a_0$
Expectation value $\langle r \rangle$	$\frac{3}{2}a_0$ (for $n = 1$)	a_0

This result suggests that the Bohr orbits can be understood as the classical limit of a strongly constrained quantum system. Future work may explore whether similar sequential restrictions yield the Bohr-Sommerfeld quantization rules for more complex atoms, or whether this approach can be extended to relativistic systems via the Dirac equation.

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the language and improving the fluency of this manuscript. DeepSeek also contributed to the development of the Python scripts used to generate the figures.

A Explicit Verification of the Laplacian Difference

For a function $f(r)$ that depends only on r :

$$\nabla_{3D}^2 f(r) = f''(r) + \frac{2}{r}f'(r) \quad (30)$$

$$\nabla_{2D}^2 f(r) = f''(r) + \frac{1}{r} f'(r) \quad (31)$$

Thus:

$$(\nabla_{3D}^2 - \nabla_{2D}^2) f(r) = \frac{1}{r} f'(r) = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} f(r) \quad (32)$$

This confirms the difference operator $\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r}$.

B Atomic Units Conversion

Table 3: Atomic units and their SI equivalents.

Quantity	Atomic unit	SI value
Length	a_0	0.529×10^{-10} m
Energy	Hartree	27.2114 eV

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